

responses are well described by the Random Parasitoid Equation and are characterized by the parameters a and T_h . Thus, the respective curves may be compared to the curve obtained using pooled data.

We used two simple statistical methods to compare the response curves of the parasitoid *Cardiochiles philippinensis* attacking larvae of *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis*. In the F -test, the residual sums of squares (RSS) of each separate curve were totaled and compared with the RSS of the pooled curve (see table).

In the nonparametric rank-sums test, a single functional response curve was fitted to the pooled data, and residuals computed. The residuals for each sample

Parameter estimates (\pm asymptotic SEs) of the Random Parasitoid Equation of *Cardiochiles philippinensis* attack at different larval stages of *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis*.

Larval instar	a	T_h	RSS ^a	CV (%)
Second	1.53 \pm 1.29	0.60 \pm 0.09	46.56	76.8
Third	2.81 \pm 1.75	0.28 \pm 0.03	50.83	43.9
Fourth	7.11 \pm 15.85	0.55 \pm 0.06	37.98	57.9
Pooled	2.32 \pm 1.16	0.43 \pm 0.03	178.36	64.0

^aRSS = residual sum of squares.

Functional responses of the larval parasitoid *Cardiochiles philippinensis* attacking second-, third-, and fourth-larval instars of *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis*. Means (\square) are presented with SEs at 95% confidence level. The curves are generated using a and T_h estimates from the table.

were arranged in a single array, largest negative to largest positive, using PROC NPARIWAY available in SAS.

The figure shows the functional responses. The rank-sums test was highly significant ($P_{RS} = 0.0001$); the F -test was more conservative ($0.05 < P_F < 0.01$). The curve differences were primarily due to

different handling times. T_h for the third instar was 0.28, significantly lower than for the second and fourth instars (see table).

The rank-sums test does not assume normal distribution of the data and is thus a more appropriate test. \square

Co-variation between insects in a ricefield and important spider species

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Spiders are among the first arthropods to colonize wetland rice. Most common are *Pardosa* (= *Lycosa*) *pseudoannulata*, *Atypena* (= *Callitrichia*) *formosana*, and *Tetragnatha* *maxillosa*. These spiders are polyphagous predators that feed on the adults and nymphs of many insect species. The presence of spiders might influence the establishment and increase of pest populations.

We collected arthropods from an IIRRI plot at weekly intervals using an insect suction machine (FARMCOP). All species were identified and counted. The data on rice hoppers and dipterans collected during the cropping period were

linearly regressed with number of important spider species.

T. maxillosa populations appeared to be directly related to number of dipterans, suggesting a positive numerical response (see table). Similar relationships were found between *A. formosana* and BPH, WBPH, dipterans, and all hoppers.

P. pseudoannulata populations, however, were not related to BPH and WBPH.

The differences in the relationships of the three spider species to rice arthropods may be a result of different predatory habits. *T. maxillosa* is a horizontal orb-web building spider that tends to catch more flying insects. \square

Regression analysis of linear relationships between insects and spiders in ricefields. ^a IIRRI 1989.

Insects	<i>T. maxillosa</i>			<i>A. formosana</i>			<i>P. pseudoannulata</i>		
	a	b	F value	a	b	F value	a	b	F value
BPH	0.345	0.001	0.003 ns	1.152	0.174	10.970**	4.662	0.038	0.114 ns
WBPH	0.331	0.012	0.103 ns	1.221	0.143	4.041 *	4.082	-0.091	0.368 ns
GLH	0.261	0.019	2.373 ns	1.263	0.033	2.083 ns	3.997	0.153	10.218 **
Dipterans	0.146	0.268	16.348 **	1.604	-0.255	4.028 *	4.083	0.311	9.055 **
Total hoppers	0.192	0.021	3.152 ns	0.856	0.076	12.356 **	3.678	0.137	8.872 **
Totalinsects	0.019	0.011	3.047 ns	0.933	0.060	8.754 **	3.520	0.144	11.722 **

^aa = intercept, b = slope, ns = not significant, * = significant at $P < 0.05$, ** = significant at $P < 0.01$.

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